

Speculation on Quantum Probability(x) = W*(x)W(x) where W(x)=the Wavefunction

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 20, 2025

Quantum mechanics is an unusual statistical theory in many ways. One particular striking departure from classical probability is the notion of Probability(x,t) = W*(x,t)W(x,t). Here we focus on the simpler W(x), where W(x) is the wavefunction. In other words, W(x) is somewhat like a square-root of probability, a notion which does not exist in classical physics. Here, we try to speculate as to the reason for this unusual feature by considering features of different probabilities and the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ which is also the classical free particle action for $v=x/t$.

In particular, we argue that the same variable x is associated with two meanings. In $P(x)=1/L$, where L is an arbitrary length, it represents the probability for an interaction at x. From the Lorentz invariant, p(momentum)dx being independent of p means that $dx(p)=\text{constant}/p$. This is associated with a different function $F1(p,x)$ which displays the dx intervals. It is possible, however, to have a complex $F1(p,x)=\exp(ipx)$ which not only describes the intervals in x, but also the reduced information of $P(x)=1/L$ in its magnitude. The usual manner of eliminating variables that are not of interest in a probability function is to integrate them out, but here it is the same x variable which is the issue. Mathematically, using $\exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L} \exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ solves the problem. Thus, even though $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$, W(x) is not really the square-root of P(x), but rather a probability function which contains more information than P(x), but is linked to it (because P(x) contains a subset of information) in a somewhat different mathematical manner because x represents two pieces of information, possible interaction point and range of the interaction itself.

Probability and Entropy Based

Shannon's entropy is - Sum over i P(i) ln(P(i)), but as we have mentioned a number of times one may choose different P(i)'s. These are presumably based on which measurement one considers. In other words, a particle may have a set of properties $a_1, a_2, a_3 \dots$, but one may only be interested in the probability related to one, say a_2 . In such a case, $P(a_2)$ ignores the other properties altogether. A common example is $P(x)dx$ in classical physics. If one tries to measure the amount of time a bound particle spends in each constant dx, i.e. $dt(x)$, then (1) states this is proportional to a probability, ie.

$$P(x)dx = C dx/|v(x)| \quad \text{where } \frac{1}{2} m v(x)v(x) + V(x) = E \quad \text{nonrelativistic ((1))}$$

One may note that one makes random x checks to see if a particle is present. There is no interest in the direction or motion, speed, momentum, rest mass or kinetic energy of the particle even though these are also variable except for rest mass. Thus, P(x) is a probability related to a particular piece of information which is fine. If $v(x)=\text{constant}$, then:

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \quad \text{where L is an arbitrary length ((2))}$$

As we have noted previously $P(x)=1/L$ holds for different v and p values, but that is fine as one is only interested in finding the probability for a particle to be at x .

Now one might be interested in $P(x)$ in order to study possible interactions which may occur. This is only one possible scenario of interest, but we argue, an important one. In such a case, p (momentum) is proportional to the impulse and $P(x) = 1/L$ means that regardless of p , one has equal probability to have an interaction at any x .

We note that one might consider different probabilities which lead to different Shannon entropies. For example, if one has $v_1(x)$ and $v_2(x)$ in two different boxes with the initial condition of $t=0$ $x=0$, one might ask for $P(\text{positive momentum})$ and $P(\text{negative momentum})$ with a restriction on the length of time. For example, if $v_2=2 v_1 = \text{constant}$ and chooses $T=\text{half a period of } v_1$, then v_1 is always positive while v_2 is positive half the time. This leads to two different probability schemes even though $P(x)=1/L$ in both cases. Thus, $P(i)$ is based on the i variable of interest.

Given that $P(x)=1/L$ for constant p (constant v) one might ask How is this related to the quantum result?

$P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)=\text{the wavefunction}$ and we ignore time for simplicity ((2))

In classical physics, there is no need to consider a kind of square root $W(x)$. For a free particle, $W(x)=\exp(ipx)$ and so one has information about p (momentum), but $P(x)$ is only concerned with position. A priori, it seems that there is no reason to be interested in momentum as affecting $P(x)$. A problem, we suggest, arises with a result from special relativity, a theory which is also considered to be classical.

A Contradiction Introduced by Special Relativity

$P(x)dx=dx/L$ for $p=\text{constant}$ seems to be a straightforward classical result which suggests that one has equal probability to find a particle at any x in L regardless of p (or v for that matter). We use p to make a comparison with special relativity.

Special relativity on the other hand yields the Lorentz invariant (one dimension):

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((1))$$

This means that for $x=vt$, each x,t pair have a different A value. Ignoring t , even px represents a different A number for each x as well. Now, A is equivalent to the classical action Lagrangian* time for $v=x/t$. (This result holds also in the free particle relativistic case.) Thus, A having a different value at each x suggests that each x does not have the same weight. This result follows because A is a dynamical expression, but px is not. px yields different results for different p when $P(x)=1/L$ suggests that each x carries the same weight. Given that one really deals with dx regions (and not a point x physically), we suggest that for:

$P(x)=1/L$ to be compatible with pdx for all x in L one must have: $dx=\text{constant}/p$ ((2))

The problem with this result is that $dx = \text{constant}/p$ suggests different sized dx regions for different p , although each is supposed to be completely consistent with $P(x)dx = dx/L$. In other words, for a given p , one may use whatever gradation for breaking L into dx values. In particular, if one were to measure $P(x)$ one would use a dx interval in a measurement and so dx is required. By making pdx consistent with $P(x) = 1/L$, one has a $dx(p) = \text{constant}/p$.

Now $P(x) = 1/L$ is a function which holds for all x , while the $\text{constant}/p = dx$ scenario suggests an x at the center of each $dx(p)$ interval. In other words, one does not have a continuous function in x which is problematic mathematically especially because $P(x)dx = dx/L$ follows as dx becomes very small. Formally one has:

$P(x \text{ in an interval}) = 1 / (L/dx(p))$ i.e the number of intervals possible is a function of p and one sums over the number of intervals and no longer integrates over dx ((3))

((3)) means that one no longer has a constant $P(x) = 1/L$, but physically this cannot be the case because an interaction (p striking a target) may occur at any x . One cannot allow an interval size linked to p stop one from placing a target at any x value as measured by a very high frequency photon. Furthermore, $dx = \text{constant}/p$ was introduced in the first place to make special relativity consistent with $P(x) = 1/L$ and so one cannot then introduce ((3)) which is not consistent. As a result, one has a paradox. One must have gradations along x , $dx = \text{constant}/p$, suggesting a corresponding distribution $F1(p,x)$, while at the same time one must also have $P(x)dx = dx/L$. Furthermore, $F1(p,x)$ cannot be $1/L$.

The question then becomes: How is $F1(p,x)$ related to $1/L$, if at all? The constraints seem to be:

- (A) Regardless of the value of constant p , an interaction may occur at any x and so $P(x) = 1/L$ has physical meaning.
- (B) Each p value has its own $dx(p)$ with presumably a distribution within this region which is not $1/L$.

We suggest that in order to resolve the contradiction, one needs to examine the constraints associated with each statement. Both are linked to an interaction we argue if one considers p as a variable of consideration. (A) indicates the possible location of an interaction regardless of $dx(p)$. This suggests that $\text{constant}/p$ is somehow associated with the specifics of the interaction. In other words, different p values may discern different dx intervals (of an interacting object such as a 2-slit apparatus) regardless of the x position at which the object is placed. There is equal probability for an interaction to occur at any x , but at given x , there is the notion of a $dx(p) = \text{constant}/p$ which should have physical implications.

This seems to suggest $P(x) = 1/L$ and $F1(p,x)$ being more or less independent as one may first choose an x point and then impose $dx(p) = \text{constant}/p$ on this point. The problem is that $F1(p,x)$ (creating $dx(p)$) breaks $P(x) = 1/L$ and one is forced to deal with two independent probability schemes $1/L$ and $F1(p,x)$ which contradict each other.

A second issue exists, namely that of the particle instantaneously creating a $dx(p) = \text{constant}/p$ interval at the x point of interaction. The x point of interaction has nothing to do with the particle motion and so one would suggest that the $dx(p)$ already exists for the particle regardless of the

x interaction point. In such a case, the $dx(p)$ pattern exists in x space just as $1/L$ exists in x space, even though the two are different functions. We have argued that one, namely $1/L$, may be said to represent the position of the particle and the other its interaction range. If this is the case, then one might argue that $F1(p,x)$ must not only display the $dx(p)$ in space, but also manifest $1/L$, whereas $P(x)=1/L$ is independent of p.

It seems like a contradiction for $F1(p,x)$ to represent $1/L$ for all x while at the same time displaying $dx(p)$ intervals. If $F1(p,x)=0$ at the interval initial and endpoints, then a real function cannot simultaneously represent $1/L$. Mathematically, one could consider a complex function which can manifest two different properties:

- (A) A magnitude property which is a constant
- (B) A frequency property which changes in x

Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ could be a solution for $F1(p,x)$. This solution contains both the information about $1/L$ through a constant magnitude and the $dx(p)$ interval through the periodicity of $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. In such a case, one does not really need $F1(p,x)$ and $1/L$, but as noted above, one may create probabilities which only consider a certain variable and ignore others. $F1(p,x)$ considers the variables p and x and shows both a constant magnitude (linked to $1/L$) and a periodicity in x. This is necessary information for the specifics of an interaction, but more information than one needs to show that an interaction may occur at any point x, i.e. for $P(x)$. One only needs the magnitude for that situation and so one may extract this necessary information through:

$$P(x) = 1/L = \exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L} \exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L} \quad ((4))$$

W(x) is not the Square Root of Probability

As a result, we argue that $F1(p,x) = W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \exp(ipx)$ and $P(x)=1/L$ are different probability functions, but that $F1(p,x)=W(x)$ contains the information about $P(x)$. We noted in the first paragraph that one may create probability functions of different variables. $P(x)$ happens to be such a probability and $F1(p,x)=W(x)$ another. It is possible for one probability function to contain information about another even in classical probability. The usual approach, however, of extracting information about the variable of interest is to integrate over the other variables. Here, the variable of interest x takes on two different meanings. The first is:

- (A) The position of the interaction
- (B) The nature of the interaction in x

Thus, one cannot simply integrate out one or the other. A different mathematical scheme is needed to simultaneously describe the two different behaviours in the same x variable and so the magnitude of $\exp(ipx)$ becomes the signature of $P(x)=1/L$ and ((4)) is needed to extract $P(x)$ from $W(x)=F1(p,x)$ instead of performing the usual integration.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may create various different probability functions depending on what variable or property is of interest. We consider the classical probability for a constant speed (hence constant p) in a length L , i.e. $P(x)dx=dx/L$. This implies that an interaction may occur at any x with the same probability regardless of the value of p . Different p values yield different impulses, but that has nothing to do with the position of the target.

We note, however, that special relativistic Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ assigns a different A value to each x point. A happens to be the classical free particle action Lagrangian*time (both relativistically and nonrelativistically) and describes dynamics and so there is no problem for A to be different. $P(x)=1/L$ does not describe specific dynamics, only relative dynamics, i.e each $dt(x)$ is the same regardless of v or p . The problem, we argue, is that even the px piece of the Lorentz invariant suggests different weights for different x points. We note that one really measures a dx interval and so consider pdx and argue that given $P(x)=1/L$, one should have a $dx(p)=\text{constant}/p$ to remove this p bias. This leads to a contradiction because one now has a $dx(p)$ interval which suggests that $P(x)$ is not $1/L$. We try to interpret the meaning of the two uses of the variable x .

First, $1/L=P(x)$ means that one may have an interaction at any x point, while $dx(p)=\text{constant}/p$ suggests an uncertainty or probability in space at the x point linked to interaction details/range. We further suggest that one cannot arbitrarily assign $dx(p)$ onto any x point where a target may happen to sit, but rather the $dx(p)$ pattern should exist in space. We suggest a function $F1(p,x)$ which describes the $dx(p)$ intervals, but at the same $P(x)=1/L$. In other words, $P(x)$ is a less informative probability than $F1(p,x)$. It is fine to have different probability functions for different sets of information. The usual approach is to have a function $P(x1,x2,x3)$ and to integrate over the variables that are not of interest. Here, one has the same variable x which has no meanings. The first, related to $P(x)=1/L$ describes at which point an interaction may occur while $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ describe $dx(p)$ intervals linked with the actual interaction mechanism. Thus, one cannot simply integrate out one meaning. Instead, $W(x)=\text{wavefunction}=F1(p,x)$ is a probability function which contains more information than $P(x)=1/L$. Instead of integrating a variable to find $P(x)$, one uses $\exp(-ipx)/\text{sqrt}(L)$ $\exp(ipx)/\text{sqrt}(L)$ instead.

References

1. Majernik, V. and Opatrny, T. Entropic Uncertainty Relations and the Harmonic Oscillator (J. Phys. A Math, 1996)
<http://www.ktf.upol.cz/tom/clanky/jpa96-ent.pdf>